

**21st Century Attributes and Skills of a Teacher in the
Perspective of College Students**

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Abstract

Teaching is an ever evolving field of profession which comprises a magnitude of skills, talent, and dedication. This descriptive study intended to revisit some primary characteristics of a 21st century teacher in the standpoint of 123 conveniently selected college students. The findings of the study were as follows: The respondents answered *Agree* on the context of professional and personal attributes that a teacher should possess; while in terms of the primary skills exhibited by a teacher, it got an answer of *Very Satisfactory*. Significant differences were observed in Professional Attributes, Learning and Innovation Skills and Life Career Skills when grouped according to respondent's profile. Furthermore, there was a low to moderate evidence of relationship that existed between the Attributes of a teacher and skills. This was further confirmed through regression analysis and found out that the attributes of a teacher significantly affects the teaching skills. Based on the findings, practical suggestion on professional and personal improvements of a teacher were discussed and recommended.

Keywords: Attributes, Skills, Perspective of college students, 21st century teacher, teaching

Introduction

In the 21st century curriculum, change always plays a vital role for adopting newer and better set of teaching strategies and principles which will again put teachers into the test of tides in terms of their teaching attributes and skills. A good teacher is more than just an educator. The characteristics that make a teacher good are complex and extensive. (Bullock, 2015)

Education is such a great motivator and at the same time a source of investment. Policy makers are revolutionizing teacher evaluation by attaching greater stakes to student test scores and observation-based teacher effectiveness measures, but relatively little is known about why they often differ so much. (Harris, Ingle, Rutledge, 2014) But naturally, the results of these tests will not decide the future of students, reality will hone their skills and merging with the society will also have a great impact towards the holistic development of students. Educating a nation of culturally, ethnically/racially, and linguistically diverse students is one of the many challenges facing teachers and teacher educators, resulting in teachers questioning their ability to improve learning for these groups. (Chu, 2011)

Over the years of teaching practice and innovation, several attempts were used to quantify some important strategies and methodologies in teaching. In the words of Gargani & Strong, (2014) Teacher observations have become a national education phenomenon, mandated by federal policies and promoted by philanthropists. They are crucial components of teacher evaluation systems that often have high stakes for teachers and school systems, but have sparked little innovation. A study also found out that rating instruments, including disposition surveys, clinical practice observation, ratings and portfolio assessment each measure a single underlying dimension rather than the multiple constructs they were designed to measure. (Henry, Thompson, Campbell, Patriarca, Luterbach, Lys & Covington, 2013)

On the other hand, the associations of both positive and negative relationship (teacher-student) with a student's school engagement were medium to large, whereas associations with a students' school achievement were small to medium. (Roorda, Koomen, Spilt & Oort, 2011). Furthermore, stronger effects were found in high grades and negative effects of relationships were stronger in primary than in secondary. Accordingly, Loeb, Soland & Fox (2014) exposed that teachers who were effective with English learners also tend to be effective with their non-English learners and vice versa. There was also evidence that some teachers are relatively more effective with English learners than with non-English learners and that this increased efficacy is predicted by a teacher's fluency in students' home language and whether he or she possesses a bilingual teaching certificate.

Moreover, emotions experienced by teachers while teaching are relatively unexplored avenues of research (Coleman, 2014). Emotional discomfort was a central theme as the teacher considered the children's play in relation to the knowledge acquired in the graduate online course or vice versa. (Madrid, Baldwin & Frye, 2013) More specifically, the findings of the study revealed the teacher's discomfort and the resulting struggle and ambivalence she encountered as new information about the children's social worlds disrupted her prior beliefs, values, and feelings.

On the other side of the discussion, Baric and Burusic (2014) suggested that teachers with different professional status-related personal attributes are fairly uniform in their views, expectations, and satisfactions. Furthermore, they found it interesting to note about the relationship between school-based Catholic religious education and the parish-based catechesis, where existing relationship represent weak source of religious education teacher's satisfaction. For Amatea, Cholewa, Mixon (2012), they investigated a course at a large research university in

the Southeastern United States designed to influence the attitudes of pre-service teachers (PSTs) about how they might work with low-income and/or ethnic minority families and found out that their attitudes were less stereotypic, they were more confident about using family-centric involvement practices, and conceptualized student's problems in less blaming terms.

Local authors also share some important and revealing literatures. Based on the study of Magno & Sambrano (2016), it was found out that the teachers practicing learner-centered approaches use their self-efficacy in order to be effective in teaching but it was also found out that being effective does not result in high teaching performance rating. On the other hand, Enanoza & Abao (2014) revealed that teachers generally carried out their roles excellently; likewise, there were significant interrelationships between and among the roles as well as the factors that affect them. The physical, psychological, emotional, and spiritual factors directly affect the successful exercise of their roles. Moreover, Espina (2013) described the ideal teacher as one primarily with "ability to share relevant knowledge and experiences to clarify concept." Also, "expertise in the subject matters taught" was identified as the most prevalent descriptor of the assessed teacher. Likewise, teachers were seen to be effective in instructional delivery and facilitating learning with premium placed on humane treatment of learners. Lastly, De Guzman, Torres, Uy, Tancioco, Siy & Hernandez (2008) identified clusters of teacher roles that indicate caring behavior that imply acts of teaching become acts of caring depending on how the teachers, the efficient cause of education, perform their ordinary tasks in the context of extraordinariness. Interestingly, the extent to which teachers' caring behavior is felt and experienced by the students positively shapes their orientations as cared for individuals.

This study focused on the idea of identifying the attributes and skills of a teacher in the viewpoint of the college students in the 21st century curriculum. The paper hopes to provide

essential information about teacher's attributes and skills in the fascinating world of teaching career. Lastly, to add up to the research world some substantial data that would be very beneficial for future researchers who will endeavor in the same field with more enthusiasm and in depth analysis.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used the descriptive research method with the questionnaire as the main instrument for gathering data. The study intended to analyze and interpret data that was gathered through the survey and later on describe its characteristics.

Since the study was concerned with attributes and skills of a teacher as perceived by students in college, the descriptive method, therefore, is the most convenient method to utilize for the investigation.

Respondents

The researcher utilized 123 participants in this study from the different colleges in Olongapo City and Zambales area using convenience sampling technique. The respondents were bona fide students, currently enrolled and studying within the semester of academic year 2017-2018, in the different institutions in Olongapo City and Zambales province.

Instrument

A draft questionnaire was made by the researchers. It was then submitted for critiquing to several professors who are practitioners in the field of research for validity and reliability. Their comments were considered in revising and finalizing the construction of the questionnaire. To

further test the clarity and validity of the questionnaire, it was first tested among students who were not included as subject participants in the study.

Statistical Treatment

In this study, Regression Analysis, Pearson-R, ANOVA, T-test, frequency count, and weighted mean were utilized. All data and information were gathered in order to be tallied, tabulated, classified, analyzed, and interpreted. The weighted values assigned to the awareness of college students were patterned after Likert Scaling.

Results and Discussion

The following tables represent the overall results of the study and were comprehensively analyzed and interpreted with discussion alongside it.

Table 1. Mean Distribution of Respondents on the Professional Attributes of a Teacher

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1) Has the mastery of the subject matter.	3.60	Strongly Agree
2) Is a model of best teaching practice.	3.49	Agree
3) Works with the stakeholders (parents, community, school, and teachers) in the school setting.	3.14	Agree
4) Instructs children in classrooms with the best teaching practice.	3.39	Agree
5) Has characters and skills to approach all aspects of his/ her work.	3.24	Agree
6) Views “learning” as a lifelong process for everyone.	3.26	Agree
7) Have the characters and skills for working towards improving his/ her teaching.	3.30	Agree
8) Have qualities and skills for working towards improving the school.	3.31	Agree
9) Has the knowledge to guide the science and art of his/ her teaching practice.	3.19	Agree
10) Perceives himself/ herself as someone who can affect change or learning.	3.32	Agree
11) Sees to it that teaching is a noble profession.	3.25	Agree
12) Should manifest genuine enthusiasm and pride in teaching.	3.35	Agree

13) Participates in the continuing professional learning education program.	3.33	Agree
14) Uses the teaching profession as a dignified means of earning a decent living.	3.25	Agree
15) Possesses a spirit of professional loyalty, mutual confidence, and faith in one another.	3.33	Agree
Overall Mean	3.32	Agree

Table 1 exhibits the mean distribution of respondents on the professional attributes of a teacher. It can be analyzed that Statement 1 got the highest mean with 3.60 which has a descriptive equivalent of Strongly Agree, while statement 3 got the lowest mean with 3.14 which is equivalent to Agree. To sum it up, the overall mean for the professional attributes of a teacher was pegged at 3.32 with a descriptive rating of Agree. According to Magno & Sembrano (2017), they stipulated in their study that being effective does not result in high teaching performance ratings. This result may partially coincide with the result of the study.

Table 2. Mean Distribution of Respondents on the Personal Attributes of a Teacher

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
1) Passionate for teaching and cares for their students.	3.69	Strongly Agree
2) Entertaining in relating with students which stimulate a friendly relationship.	3.37	Agree
3) Models of values and brings standards, code of ethics, and strong beliefs.	3.47	Agree
4) Open in promoting respect and trust between teachers and students.	3.45	Agree
5) Fair and impartial in treating students which eliminates discrimination.	3.39	Agree
6) Objective and unbiased in judging their work and performance.	3.46	Agree
7) Sincere to show their real self, without any dishonesties and half-truths.	3.36	Agree
8) Accepts mistakes and faults without cover-up.	2.98	Agree
9) Upright and exemplary in behavior to earn respect and high esteem from students and colleagues.	3.11	Agree
10) Patient with their students' limitations and difficulties.	3.17	Agree
11) Attends to difficult classroom situations with cool-headedness.	3.29	Agree
12) Full of energy and cheerfulness which will be felt by children.	3.20	Agree

13) Eager and excited, full of passion and love, which can be observed by children.	3.50	Strongly Agree
14) Committed to perform the duties and responsibilities mandated by the laws and code of ethics of the profession.	3.37	Agree
15) Able to perform all teaching and learning activities with consistency and selflessness to the best interest of the students.	3.54	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.36	Agree

Table 2 shows the mean distribution of respondents on the personal attributes of a teacher. It can be understood from the table that Statement 1 got the highest mean with 3.69 which has a corresponding descriptive rating of Strongly Agree, while Statement 8 got the lowest with 2.98 which is equivalent to Agree in the descriptive rating scale. Overall, the mean was 3.36 which was interpreted as Agree. However, based on the result of the study of Harris, Ingle & Rutledge (2014), they suggested that the method of evaluation may not only affect which specific teachers are rewarded in the short term, but shape the qualities of teacher and teaching students experience in the long term.

Table 3. Mean Distribution of Respondents on the Skills of a Teacher

Criteria	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Communication Skills		
1) Knows teamwork in the learning environment	3.54	Excellent
2) Able to collaborate with other key players in learning	3.20	Very Satisfactory
3) Have good interpersonal skills *	3.25	Very Satisfactory
4) Well-oriented with the local, national, and global environment	3.32	Very Satisfactory
5) Possesses positive interactive communication skills	3.22	Very Satisfactory
Learning and Innovation Skills		
1) Creative in every aspect of learning domain	3.33	Very Satisfactory
2) Shows curiosity to students' learning and expresses his ideas enthusiastically	3.37	Very Satisfactory
3) Possesses critical thinking and problem solving skills	3.36	Very Satisfactory
4) Knows when and how to take risks at times	3.23	Very Satisfactory
5) Capable of outcome-based leaning for effective student evaluation	3.29	Very Satisfactory
Information, Media, and Technology Skills		
1) Able to evaluate, apply, or create conceptual visual representations	3.29	Very Satisfactory

2) Able to critically analyze messages that inform, entertain, and sell to us every day	2.80	Very Satisfactory
3) Able to understand scientific concepts and processes required for personal decision making.	2.89	Very Satisfactory
4) Able to apply basic economic concepts in situations relevant to one's life	2.98	Very Satisfactory
5) Able to responsibly use appropriate technology to communicate, solve problems, etc.	3.21	Very Satisfactory
Life and Career Skills		
1) Able to adapt and be flexible in every context of teaching	3.40	Very Satisfactory
2) Shows leadership quality and responsibility towards work	3.45	Very Satisfactory
3) Concerned with social issues and cross-cultural events	3.33	Very Satisfactory
4) Have strong initiative and self-direction towards success and meeting goals	3.11	Very Satisfactory
5) Accountable in every decision he/she made in life.	3.41	Very Satisfactory
Overall Mean for Skills	3.25	Very Satisfactory

Table 3 displays the mean distribution of respondents on skills of a teacher. It can be examined that in the section of Communication Skills, Statement 1 and Statement 2 got the highest and lowest means with 3.54 and 3.20 and they have a descriptive interpretation of Excellent and Very Satisfactory respectively; while in Learning and Innovation Skills, Statement 2 got the highest mean with 3.37 and Statement 4 got the lowest mean with 3.23, both with a descriptive rating of Very Satisfactory; on Information, Media, and Technology, the highest mean was obtained by Statement 1 and statement 2 got the lowest with 3.29 and 2.80 respectively, both got the same descriptive rate of Very Satisfactory; and lastly, for Life and Career Skills, Statement 2 got the highest mean with 3.45 which was equivalent to Very Satisfactory in the Descriptive Rating Scale and Statement 4 got the lowest mean with 3.11 which was also interpreted as Very Satisfactory in the rating scale. The overall mean score for the skills of a teacher was 3.25, interpreted as Very Satisfactory. This result is supported by the study of Espina (2013) where he related that teachers were seen to be effective in instructional delivery and facilitating learning with premium placed on humane treatment of learners.

Table 4. T-test for Significant Difference on the Professional and Personal Attribute of a Teacher when grouped according to Sex

	Male		Female		<i>t</i> - test
	M	SD	M	SD	
Professional Attributes	3.19	.497	3.40	.474	-2.355*
Personal Attributes	3.28	.434	3.40	.412	-1.522

* $p < 0.05$

Table 4 indicates the T test for significant difference on the professional and personal attributes of a teacher when grouped according to sex. It can be deduced from the table that there exist a significant difference in the professional attributes of a teacher, since $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -2.355$ and $p < 0.05$. However, on the personal attributes of a teacher there was no significant difference found since $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -1.522$ and $p > 0.05$. To sum it up, the male respondents have a different kind of perspective when it comes to professional attributes of a teacher. On the other hand, in terms of personal attributes, both sexes are have the same perspectives. Based on the study of Alhija (2017), there exists a salient difference in the students' perception of good teaching in terms of gender of which the current study have also observed.

Table 5. T-test for Significant Difference on the Professional and Personal Attribute of a Teacher when grouped according to Type of School

	Public		Private		<i>t</i> - test
	M	SD	M	SD	
Professional Attributes	3.18	.57	3.39	.43	-2.244*
Personal Attributes	3.31	.46	3.38	.40	-.954

* $p < 0.05$

Table 5 shows the T-test for significant difference of the professional and personal attributes of a teacher when grouped according to the type of school. It can be deduced that Professional Attributes got a $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -2.244$ which corresponds to $p < 0.05$ can be considered a significant finding, while Personal Attributes showed no significant difference for it

yielded a $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -0.954$ which has a $p > 0.05$. To summarize, the professional attributes of a teacher is seen differently when the respondents came from public or private institution. In a study by Baric & Burusic (2014), they revealed an interesting finding between the relationship of school-based Catholic religious education and parish-based catechesis, where it represents a weak source of religious education and teaching satisfaction. Although it has no direct relationship with the result of the study, it has an indirect proof that the type of school can influence the result of the study at hand.

Table 6. T-test for Significant Difference on the Skills of a Teacher when grouped according to Type of School

	Public		Private		<i>t</i> - test
	M	SD	M	SD	
Communication Skills	3.20	.62	3.36	.59	-1.429
Learning And Innovation Skills	3.11	.69	3.42	.55	-2.705*
Information, Media & Technology Skills	2.91	.60	3.09	.54	-1.701
Life & Career Skills	3.11	.67	3,46	.53	-3.158*

* $p < 0.05$

Table 6 indicates the T-test for significant difference on the skills of a teacher when grouped according to the type of school. There was a significant difference found in the section of Learning and Innovation Skills with $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -2.705$, $p < 0.05$ and Life and Career Skills $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -3.158$, $p < 0.05$. On the other hand, Communication Skills got a $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -1.429$, $p > 0.05$ and Information, Media and Technology Skills got a $t(121, 2 \text{ tailed}) = -1.701$ with $p > 0.05$. Both scores did not yield sufficient result to be considered significant. Overall, Learning and Innovation Skills, together with Life and Career Skills provided a different perspective among the respondents of the study which is influenced by the type of institution where they came from. According to Magno & Sembrano (2017), teachers practicing learner-centered approaches use their self-efficacy in order to be effective in teaching, but being

effective does not result in high teaching performance rating. However, this idea is in contrast with the current study.

Table 7. ANOVA for Significant Difference on Skills of a Teacher when grouped according to Year Level

Skills		SS	Df	MS	<i>F</i> <i>computed</i>
Communication Skills	Between Groups	2.78	3	.93	2.647
	Within	41.72	119	.35	
	Total	44.51	122		
Learning And Innovation Skills	Between Groups	6.180	3	2.06	6.057*
	Within	40.47	119	.34	
	Total	46.65	122		
Information, Media & Technology Skills	Between Groups	1.48	3	.49	1.554
	Within	37.85	119	.32	
	Total	39.34	122		
Life & Career Skills	Between Groups	4.83	3	1.61	4.824*
	Within	39.74	119	.33	
	Total	44.57	122		

* $p < 0.05$

Table 7 shows the ANOVA for significant difference on skills of a teacher when grouped according to year level. It can be seen from the table that Learning and Innovation Skills and Life and Career Skills got significant results since $F(3,119) = 6.057, p < 0.05$ and $F(3,119) = 4.824, p < 0.05$ respectively. However, there were no significant findings from Communication Skills and Information, Media, and Technology Skills since $F(3,119) = 2.647, p > 0.05$ and $F(3,119) = 1.554, p > 0.05$ respectively. To generalize, Learning and Innovation Skills and Life and Career Skills provided a different viewpoint among the respondents depending on the year level that they belong to. Onwuegbuzie et al. (2007) analyzed that with respect to the level of students, graduate students revealed a statistically significant result compared to other types of students in their study. The result of the study is indirectly related with the current study's results.

Table 8. ANOVA for Significant Difference on Attributes of a Teacher when grouped according to Age

Attributes		SS	Df	MS	<i>F</i> <i>computed</i>
Professional	Between Groups	2.91	4	.73	3.22*
	Within	26.63	118	.23	
	Total	29.53	122		
Personal	Between Groups	.61	4	.15	.85
	Within	21.21	118	.18	
	Total	21.82	122		

* $p < 0.05$

Table 3.2 shows the Analysis of Variance for significant difference on the Professional and Personal Attributes of a teacher when grouped according to Age. It can be deduced that there exists a significant difference on the Professional Attribute since $F(4,118) = 3.219, p < 0.05$, while Personal Attributes got no significant result since $F(4,118) = 0.853, p > 0.05$. To simplify, the Professional Attributes considerably made a significant difference among the respondents when they were grouped according to age; thus, maturity comes into perspective. According to Enanoza & Abao (2014), a teacher's physical, psychological, emotional, and spiritual well-being greatly affects the performance and exercise of his/ her roles which indirectly supports the results of this study.

Table 9. ANOVA for Significant Difference on Skills of a Teacher when grouped according to Age

Skills		SS	Df	MS	<i>F</i> <i>computed</i>
Communication Skills	Between Groups	1.47	4	.37	1.01
	Within	43.03	118	.37	
	Total	44.41	122		
Learning And Innovation Skills	Between Groups	2.45	4	.66	1.77
	Within	44.01	118	.37	
	Total	46.65	122		
Information, Media & Technology Skills	Between Groups	1.26	4	.32	0.98
	Within	38.07	118	.32	
	Total	39.34	122		

Life & Career Skills	Between Groups	3.46	4	.87	2.48*
	Within	41.11	118	.35	
	Total	44.57	122		

* $p < 0.05$

Table 9 points out the ANOVA of significant difference on Skills of a teacher when grouped according to Age. It can be analyzed that only Life and Career Skills got a significant findings since $F(4,118) = 2.483, p < 0.05$. However, the rest of the Skills got no significant outcomes and got the following values: Communication Skills, $F(4,118) = 1.011, p > 0.05$; Learning and Innovations Skills, $F(4,118) = 1.774, p > 0.05$; and Information, Media, and Technology Skills, $F(4,118) = 0.978, p > 0.05$. The results have some connection with the study of Gu & Day (2013) when they stated that the experience of resilience amongst teacher was perceived as being closely allied to their everyday capacity to sustain their educational purposes and successfully manage the unavoidable uncertainties which are inherent in the practice of being a teacher.

Table 10. Correlation Matrix on the Attributes and Skills

	Professional Attribute	Personal Attribute
Communication Skills	.528*	.584*
Learning And Innovation Skills	.494*	.430*
Information, Media & Technology Skills	.369*	.359*
Life & Career Skills	.468*	.457*

* $p < 0.05$

Table 10 exhibits the results of the correlation analysis. It can be deduced that the four criteria of the Skills of a teacher correlated positively and significantly to the Professional and Personal Attributes of a teacher. This was shown by the obtained coefficients of 0.528, 0.494, 0.369, 0.468, and 0.541 for the Professional Attributes and 0.584, 0.430, 0.359, 0.457, and 0.532 for the Personal Attributes. The findings indicate that in general, the higher the Skills of a teacher, the higher the Professional and Personal Attributes. Conversely, the lower the Skills of a

teacher, the lower the Professional and Personal Attributes. This result is somewhat related to the findings of Soine & Lumpe (2014) wherein there was a slight, but significant, correlation between Active Learning in Classroom and teachers' use of new knowledge and skills, as measured by classroom observation scores.

Table 11. Regression Analysis for factors that Affect Attributes of a Teacher

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	p-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.801	.181		9.956	.000
Communication skills	-.279	.128	.418	2.183*	.031
Information, Media & Technology Skills	-.044	.107	-.063	-.414	.680
Life & Career Skills	.071	.127	.106	.556	.579
Learning & Innovation Skills	.158	.306	.202	.514	.608

Note: Constant = 1.801, $F(4,119) = 21.120^*$, $p < 0.05$, $R^2 = .415$

Table 11 displays the result of the regression line analysis and it can be claimed that Communication Skills yielded with B coefficient lower than the significance level set at 0.05. This means that Communication Skills is a significant determinant for the Attributes of a Teacher.

In general, the other factors also correlated positively but not to a significant extent. This means that the factors, specifically Information, Media, and Technology Skills and Life and Career Skills also account for the Attributes of a teacher. The result is in agreement with Curwood's (2014) study which indicated that teachers use language and other semiotic resources to express their own identity as well as to acknowledge, expand on, and counter others' identity claims.

Conclusion

Most of the respondents answered “Agree” on the Professional and Personal Attributes of a teacher while they responded “Very Satisfactory” on the Skills of a teacher.

There were significant differences found in Professional Attributes, Learning and Innovation Skills, Life and Career Skills when grouped according to Sex, Type of School, Year Level, and Age.

In terms of relationship, there was a low to moderate correlation between Attributes and Skills of a teacher. This is supported by the regression analysis, and Communication Skills is a significant determinant of the Attributes of a teacher while both Professional and Personal Attributes determine the Skills of a teacher.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the research conducted and the conclusions made thru the gathered data, the researcher recommends that:

- 1) Teachers, instructors, and faculty should also exhibit visibility and cooperation with the stakeholders.
- 2) School administrators should also initiate and participate in community extension programs which will provide exposure for the school staff especially the teachers.
- 3) Annual psychological and emotional check-up for teaching personnel and necessary stress debriefing after year-end teaching.
- 4) Equip the teachers with the necessary information, media, and technology through workshops and trainings to keep up with the pace of the generation.

- 5) Provide teachers options to improve their status of living, opportunities for better life, and accommodations after retirement.
- 6) Continuous updates and upgrades in the teaching skills and personality development of teachers.
- 7) Conduct future researches of this type of study.

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